

also confirmed by direct comparison with an authentic sample. In a similar manner, compound-E, m.p. 169–71°; $[\alpha]_D$, was confirmed to be stigmasterol.

The methanolic extract on standing for 48 h furnished a solid (compound-F) which was filtered and crystallised from MeOH as colourless prisms, m.p. 137°; on drying it melted at 237°; $[\alpha]_D$ – 37.7° (c 1.96 EtOH); R_f 0.67 (CHCl₃ – MeOH, 4 : 1); with ferric chloride solution it gave blue colour and it dissolved readily in NaOH solution resulting an yellow coloured solution and could be regenerated on acidification (Found: C, 51.25; H, 4.89. C₁₄H₁₈O₆ requires: C, 51.27; H, 4.88%); ν_{max} (nujol) 3 380, 1 701, 1 600, 960 and 850 cm⁻¹; λ_{max} (EtOH) 277 nm (log ϵ 3.98), no shift being observed on the addition of NaOAc or boric acid; δ (CDCl₃/DMSO; 100 MHz, TMS) 3.1–4.1 (6H, m, 11-CH₂, 2,3,4,4a-H), 3.1–4.1 (3H, 3×OH), 3.82 (3H, s, OCH₃), 4.89 (1H, d, J 10 Hz, 10b-H), 5.50 (2H, br, 2×OH) and 7.02 (1H, s, 7-H); M^+ 328 (33%); m/e 208 (100%). Based on the above data, compound-F was identified as bergenin by a direct comparison with an authentic sample⁴⁻⁶. On acetylation, compound-F gave a pentaacetate, m.p. 201°; $[\alpha]_D$ – 42°, and was identified as bergenin 3,4,8,10,11-pentaacetate by direct comparison with an authentic sample. ¹H nmr spectrum (CDCl₃; 90MHz, TMS) of bergenin pentaacetate is in close agreement with that reported; m/e : 496 (60), 454 (88), 418 (39), 405 (31), 376 (54), 376 (60), 334 (40), 321 (50), 293 (21), 292 (95), 279 (65), 274 (100), 261 (50), 259 (47), 250 (45), 237 (37), 236 (18), 224 (52), 221 (30) and 208 (86); R_f 0.59 (C₆H₆ : EtOAc, 3 : 1).

This is the first report of bergenin from this plant. The work on absolute structural elucidation of compound-C, and other new and known triterpene from the methanolic extract is in progress.

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to Professor L. R. Row, Andhra University, for his encouragement and valuable suggestions.

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Sterol Composition of *Erigeron karwinskayanus*

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Manuscript received 11 April 1988, revised 8 July 1988, accepted 18 July 1988

ERIGERON karwinskayanus DC (Compositae) is one of the dozen species of genera (*Erigeron*) which grows as perennial herb in hills of Kumaon region especially in Nainital hills. Plants of this genus have been used in indigenous system of medicine¹ and also possess nematicidal properties². Previous investigators have reported the presence of pyrone glycosides³, polyacetylenes and terpenoids⁴ from aerial parts of the plant. However, no work seems to have been reported on sterol composition of the plant. In the course of isolation of nematicidal agents from plant, we isolated the sterol from petroleum ether extract of the plant. The identification and relative concentration of individual sterols are reported here for the first time.

The aerial parts of the plant were collected from the hills of Nainital during July-August, 1987. Dried powdered material (400 g) was extracted with petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°) in a Soxhlet apparatus for 48 h. Evaporations of the extract under reduced pressure afforded a residue (4.5 g), out of which 3.5 g was saponified with 10% methanolic KOH to provide yellow coloured unsaponifiable matter (1.6 g). It was taken up in ether and column chromatographed over silica gel. Elution with hexane followed by increasing amount of ether in hexane (5, 10, 15, 20%) furnished sterols in the last elute. The crude mix. was recrystallised from methanol ether (4 : 1) to provide a crystalline solid, m.p. 130–32°; it gave positive Libermann – Buchard test confirming the steroidal nature of the compound; it was homogeneous on tlc. The sterol was subjected to glc on a Hewlett – Packered 5890 A gas chromatograph fitted with G-Scot glass capillary column (36 m×0.3 mm) coated with DB-17. Temperature of the column, injector and detector were maintained at 255°, 280° respectively. It was found to contain six sterols (Table 1), which were identified by comparison of relative retention time with authentic standard. It was found to contain β -sitosterol as the major component followed by α -spinasterol, stigmasterol dihydro-spinasterol, campesterol and cholesterol. The pre-

TABLE 1
Name

Sl. no	R _t	%	Name
1.	1.00	3.74	Cholesterol (Cholest-5-en-3β-ol)
2.	1.26	5.71	Campesterol (24-Methylcholesta-5-en-3β-ol)
3.	1.34	19.4	Stigmasterol (24-Ethylcholesta-5,22-dien-3β-ol)
4.	1.50	28.02	β-Sitosterol (24-Ethylcholesta-5-en-3β-ol)
5.	1.75	23.85	α-Spinasterol (24-Ethylcholesta-7,22-dien-3β-ol)
6.	1.75	11.37	22-Dihydrospinasterol (24-Ethylcholesta-7-en-3β-ol)

sence of both Δ⁵- and Δ⁷-sterols is quite unique. The most interesting aspect is the presence of significant amount of cholesterol (3.74%) which is rare in plant kingdom and so far reported in traces, except in *Lantana indica* where it occurs in considerable amount (7%)⁵.

Acknowledgement

Two of the authors (K.C.G. and S.D.) are thankful to Indian Council of Agriculture Research, for financial support and to Dean, C.B.S. & H. for facilities.

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Chemical Constituents of *Physalis minima* var. *indica*¹

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Manuscript received 29 June 1988, accepted 18 July 1988

IN continuation of our work on the withasteroids of *Physalis peruviana*², we took up chemical investigation of *Physalis minima* var. *indica*, an annual herb of medicinal value which is distributed

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throughout the warmer parts of India^{3,4}. A systematic chemical investigation of this plant yielded seven withasteroids and two flavone glucosides in addition to β-sitosterol, its glucoside and the previously reported⁵ withaphysalin A (1). Four of these were new and the structures of these new steroids, viz. physalindicanols A and B withaminimin and withaphysalin E (2) were reported elsewhere⁶⁻⁸. The remaining compounds were identified as physalin B⁹, physalin D¹⁰, withaphysalin C¹¹ and 3-O-glucosides of kaempferol and quercetin¹², the occurrence of which in this plant is being reported here for the first time. The ¹³C nmr data of physalins B and D that have not yet been recorded in the literature are also reported here with assignment of resonance signals to different carbon atoms of these two molecules, the assignment being based on reported spectral data¹³ of related molecules and supported by their SFORD spectra.

In this communication, an unambiguous chemical proof in support of the structure of withaphysalin E (2) is provided by a one-step chemical transformation of withaphysalin A (1) to withaphysalin E acetate (2a). When a solution of withaphysalin A in glacial acetic acid was warmed at 80° for 3 h with mercuric acetate, the reaction mixture, on usual work-up, yielded withaphysalin E acetate as the sole product. The mercuric acetate induced acetoxylation of steroidal 2,5-dien-1-ones has been studied¹⁴ by us and the product has been found to be 6β-acetoxy-2,4-dien-1-one in each case. The β-orientation of the 6-acetoxy function in 2a was ascertained from the chemical shift of 19-methyl which is known to be around δ 1.24 in 6α-isomers and around δ 1.42 in its 6β-counterparts¹⁵. The exclusive formation of 6β-acetoxy derivative deserves comments and it is conjectured that the first step is the formation of a cyclic mercuronium ion¹⁶ by addition of ⁺HgOAc on 5,6-double bond from the α-side of the molecule; the exclusive formation